

E-RIHS IP

European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science IMPLEMENTATION Phase

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D6.4 Report on Cooperation Activities

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ABSTRACT

This document, entitled “Report on Cooperation Activities”, is Deliverable D6.4 of E-RIHS IP and has been elaborated in the framework of Task 6.3 “Strengthening E-RIHS cooperation on the EU scene and beyond” of the E-RIHS IP project. It reports on exchanges and cooperation activities undertaken with relevant projects, organizations, and research infrastructures, at EU and global level, with the purpose of establishing common practice policies in the framework of the future European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). The corresponding actions have been guided by the collaboration strategy that was designed and presented in the previous E-RIHS IP deliverable D6.3 “Report on Cooperation Activities: Approach and Advancement”, which in turn had as baseline the previous advances of precedent European projects, i.e. IPERION CH, E-RIHS PP and IPERION HS, aiming at the same goal. A mapping exercise has been carried out to provide the basis for selecting a number of European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures projects and landmarks and international research infrastructures and consortia, operating in physical and natural sciences and in the social and cultural innovation domains. The exchanges and outcomes of the collaborations established and/or planned with those initiatives are described in detail in this Deliverable. Due to the dynamic character of the Heritage Science field and of the national and international provision of services in the sector, the information here presented constitutes a background on which E-RIHS ERIC can build a strong cooperation network, benefiting the whole Heritage Science domain and its participants at European and global level.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
4CH	Competence Centre for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage
ANTECIPA	Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio/Brazilian National Association for Research in Technology and Heritage Science
ARCHE	Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe
(CE)LAC	(Community of) Latin American and Caribbean States
C-ERIC	Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
CNR	National Research Council of Italy
CNRS	French National Centre for Scientific Research
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSIC	Spanish National Research Council
CYI	The Cyprus Institute
DARIAH	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities
DIGILAB	DIGItal LABoratory of E-RIHS
DiSSCo	Distributed System of Scientific Collections
EASSH	European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities
EB	Enlargement Board
EC	European Commission
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
ECHOES	European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FORTH	The Foundation for Research & Technology – Hellas
FSP	Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine
GCI	Getty Conservation Institute
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group
HS	Heritage Science
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
iCNN	Interim Committee of National Nodes
IGO	Intergovernmental Organization
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science
JPI CH	Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LANCIC	Laboratorio Nacional de Ciencias para la Investigación y Conservación del Patrimonio Cultural (México)/National Science Laboratory for Research and Conservation of Cultural Heritage (Mexico)

Deliverable D6.4

MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MS/AC	Member States and Associated Countries
NG	The National Gallery, London
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
OPERAS	OPen scholarly communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities
RCH	Resilient Cultural Heritage
ResInfra	Partnership Research Infrastructures project
R&I	Research and Innovation
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)
RI-VIS	Expanding Research Infrastructure Visibility to strengthen strategic partnership
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
ZVDKS	Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia

INTRODUCTION

E-RIHS IP is the Implementation Phase project of the E-RIHS Research Infrastructure (RI). The main aim of the project is to enable the establishment of the future E-RIHS European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) and the start of its operation phase to position itself as a reference for excellent research in the wide interdisciplinary domain of Heritage Science (HS).

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Working Group Report “Monitoring of research infrastructures performance” [1] and other ESFRI documents [2] point out that structuring the international outreach of RIs is one of the key factors for their long-term sustainability [3,4]. Additionally, the 2018 C-ERIC Survey [5] estimates that 45 % of the ERICs and ESFRI Roadmap RIs include international co-operation in their statutes. E-RIHS IP is a large consortium composed of 16 National Nodes (14 founders, 2 observers) plus ICCROM, tens of institutions and hundreds of researchers working in the field of HS, a growing and highly dynamic interdisciplinary research domain that is developing fast in a worldwide scenario. In these conditions, the relevance of the future E-RIHS ERIC, the enhancement of its strategic value and the opportunities offered to HS researchers are strongly linked with: a) the possibilities of exchanging lessons learnt and acquired experience with other relevant initiatives at EU and global level (RIs, networks, projects, etc.) in the field of HS and related disciplines; and b) the elaboration of a clear collaboration strategy towards the establishment of common practice policies. On the other hand, cooperation at global level will ensure that good practices and innovative initiatives (e.g., collaborative research, transnational access platforms, training modules, outreach, management, etc.), implemented by E-RIHS partners over the last years in the framework of previous EU collaborative projects, could be mirrored or adapted by other national nodes at EU and international levels and will contribute to the development of a global RI for HS.

The international presence of E-RIHS constitutes the basis towards a Global-RIHS collaboration and will be further expanded by fostering global RI connectivity in line with Europe’s international cooperation policy objectives, with the EC High-Level Expert Group (HLEG) [6] and the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) recommendations [7], and with the Tenerife Declaration on “Global Dimension and Sustainability of Research Infrastructures” [8]. Expert guidelines on how to facilitate partnerships between RIs at global level, including the three white papers produced by the Horizon 2020 RI-VIS project [9], will be put in practice in order to raise awareness of E-RIHS activities in new communities in EU and beyond.

This document, “Report on Cooperation Activities”, is Deliverable 6.4 of E-RIHS IP and has been elaborated in the framework of Task 6.3 “Strengthening E-RIHS cooperation on the EU scene and beyond” of the project. It follows the strategy proposed and reported in the previous D6.3 Deliverable “Report on Cooperation Activities: Approach and Advancement” [10]. In D6.3, we formulated the approach that the E-RIHS IP consortium would undertake towards the establishment of a Cooperation Strategy in the broad area of HS, considering relevant networks and initiatives of various kinds and geographical influence and operating in the physical and natural sciences and in the social and cultural innovation domains. The specific objectives of the E-RIHS IP Cooperation Strategy were formulated as follows:

- To map the most relevant ESFRI projects and landmarks and international RIs and consortia with a view to identify areas of exchange and cooperation;
- To assess and strengthen connections with RIs, ERICs, projects and networks at EU and global levels when previous links have been already established, both to learn from them and to maximize the impact of E-RIHS IP activities;

- Where no previous links exist, to engage with other initiatives, selected as relevant in the mapping exercise, to cooperate with E-RIHS.

The methodology for developing and enlarging cooperation was also described in D6.3 [10]. It mainly included a mapping and targeting exercise to identify the relevant partners in an E-RIHS Cooperation Strategy and a preliminary list of specific actions. The present document expands further to describe the different exchanging activities that have been initiated and/or expanded, bearing in mind that these collaborative paths will serve to consolidate the HS domain by strengthening the E-RIHS international cooperation, by cultivating synergies and by amalgamating the HS community around E-RIHS.

It is worth mentioning that the activities described in D6.4 have benefited of fruitful interactions with task T4.2 of E-RIHS IP “E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy”, task T8.5 “Relation and synergies with European bodies and initiatives” of IPERION HS project [11], task T8.6 “International Dimension” also of IPERION HS [12] and task T1.3 “Investigation – Initiatives in Partnership Networks” of ARCHE project.

Particularly in what concerns task 4.2 “E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy” of E-RIHS IP, the international cooperation with countries that are currently not among the founding members of the E-RIHS ERIC-to-be is of extreme importance. The intensive involvement of scientists coming from those countries of the Enlargement Board has set the ground to plan for different types of involvement with E-RIHS ERIC-to-be, as potential full members or observers (Member States and Associated Countries), or to design partnership agreements to be negotiated case by case with institutions coming from Third Countries. The deliverable D4.4 “E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy” will describe in detail the strategy and process for the smart growth of E-RIHS ERIC-to-be.

As mentioned, the actions described in this document also touch ground on the previous activities carried out in the framework of IPERION HS project, particularly those described in task T8.6 “International Dimension” [12]. Despite the pandemic, that severely impaired the opening of new partnerships or the reinforcement of the existing ones, existing relationships in the American region with Mexico (LANCIC), Brazil (ANTECIPA) and USA (Getty Conservation Institute) were strengthened. In fact, common plans for future cooperation were reinvigorated by the participation of IPERION HS to the pilot on HS data interoperability of the ResInfra project (with the Community of Latin American and Caribbean States, CELAC), and through a virtual workshop on transatlantic cooperation in HS.

E-RIHS COOPERATION STRATEGY: ACTORS AND STATUS OF COOPERATION

As mentioned, a mapping and targeting exercise carried out at the beginning of the E-RIHS IP project, resulted in an initial list of European and international networks and in the assessment of the status of cooperation and possibilities to extend it further by categorizing the specific plan of action that would be adequate for each case. Exchanges include aspects such as scientific strategy, access protocols, data management, training, communication, dissemination and outreach, management, etc. In this section we describe each of these initiatives, the collaboration background, the present status of cooperation and the future perspectives. It is important to highlight that due to the dynamic character of the HS domain and the constant emergence of new projects and RIs, this list will be constantly reviewed and updated.

E-RIHS WITHIN RESEARCH POLICY ALIGNMENT INITIATIVES

This subpart describes two initiatives, JPI CH and ARCHE, that aim at structuring the European CH R&I domain towards a strengthened interdisciplinary collaboration and more research policy alignment. These cooperation activities contribute to E-RIHS's objectives to advocate for a stronger role of RIs in R&I policies at the EU scale and to solidify MS/AC engagement for RIs.

JPI CH, JOINT PROGRAMMING INITIATIVE ON CULTURAL HERITAGE

The Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage and Global Change (JPI CH) was created in 2010 based on an instrument launched by the European Commission. It is a Member-State-driven initiative bringing together national research funding organisations, ministries, and research councils from Europe to address societal challenges in the European Research Area (ERA) frame. It brings together experts, researchers, and policymakers to develop and coordinate research projects that focus on preserving and understanding Cultural Heritage, including historical sites, artifacts, and traditions.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

The collaboration between the Joint Programming Initiative on Cultural Heritage (JPI CH) and E-RIHS is a testament to their shared commitment to advancing HS within the European Research Area. This cooperation has strengthened their individual missions and contributed significantly to the preservation and understanding of Cultural Heritage on a broader scale. E-RIHS actively participates within the JPI CH Advisory group and plays a crucial role as the current vice-chair of the JPI CH Advisory and Scientific Board is Vania Virgili, E-RIHS interim Director General. The collaboration is facilitated by the Fondation des Sciences du Patrimoine's (FSP) role. The FSP hosts the JPI CH Secretariat since 2018, as well as the French National Node of E-RIHS. Its involvement in E-RIHS PP (through its partners) and E-RIHS IP (directly) projects further contributed to strengthening the links between the two initiatives.

PRESENT STATUS

Approach

A Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) that was signed by both parties has four objectives:

- Address the specific objectives of the E-RIHS IP Cooperation Strategy by strengthening connections with RIs, ERICs, projects and networks at European and global level when previous links have been already established, both to learn from them and to maximize the impact of E-RIHS IP activities;
- Address the specific objectives of the JPI CH which are to improve coordination at the EU level of research on Cultural Heritage – including tangible, intangible and digital assets – by identifying short and long-term needs and priorities, and concentrate and increase human, material and financial resources allocated to Cultural Heritage research at the European level;
- Promote joint and multidisciplinary approaches to Cultural Heritage research, improve knowledge, increase awareness of citizens, policy makers and stakeholders and contribute to the building and implementation of a European Research Area dedicated to Cultural Heritage research, bringing it to the international level;
- Address common goals defended jointly by the Parties through their collaboration in ARCHE – by pursuing and emphasizing the development of CH R&I as an interdisciplinary field, facilitating

convergences, interactions and transfers, so that Cultural Heritage has a more crucial role in nurturing innovation and a stronger contribution to the EU economy, developing and making broadly available new knowledge, skills, and strategies for sustainable preservation, conservation, use and management of Cultural Heritage, and increasing the involvement and intergenerational / intercultural cooperation of citizens in the content, direction and pace of construction and transmission of Cultural Heritage – and specific such as proposing joint actions responding to needs by a more efficient use of complementary activities and funding sources.

Areas of collaboration

Five areas of collaboration are contemplated:

1. Ensuring that, within the framework of JPI CH joint transnational calls and funding schemes, successful researchers and teams can gain access to the different types of facilities and resources made available by E-RIHS. To this end, the JPI CH and E-RIHS have agreed to set up a working group on the use of infrastructures made up of partners from the two initiatives;
2. Joining efforts concerning training activities. One of the first activities will be collaborating through the HS Academy by highlighting projects funded under the JPI CH calls for proposals. Three projects were shortlisted in collaboration with the HS Academy coordinators to be presented in three webinars: one in October 2023, one in November 2023 and one in December 2023;
3. Sustaining the collaboration initiated through ARCHE on Foresight activities by setting up a joint Task Force hosted by the JPI CH Governance. This Task Force will organise regular meetings operating with a medium to long-term perspective, ensuring that their efforts are both proactive and forward-thinking, contributing to the identification of and better adapting to Cultural Heritage research priorities and challenges of tomorrow;
4. Aligning strategies and visions following the path initiated through the ARCHE project by engaging in a collaborative process to review and update the strategies and vision approximately every five years. E-RIHS and the JPI CH will be able to adapt to evolving circumstances, integrate new research findings, and respond proactively to emerging challenges in the field of Cultural Heritage;
5. Cooperating on joint activities to assess the impact of their actions and create a stronger connection in their communication activities.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Implementation of the MoU and collaboration within the ARCHE project.

ARCHE, IN THE PERSPECTIVE OF THE RESILIENT CULTURAL HERITAGE PARTNERSHIP

Following the steps of the JPI CH, the ARCHE (Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe) project was launched in September 2022 and aims to prepare the Resilient Cultural Heritage (RCH) Partnership.

ARCHE, a coordination and support action (CSA) funded by Horizon Europe 2021-2027 framework programme, is a platform for coordinating research efforts, sharing expertise, and fostering innovation in Cultural Heritage. Its primary goal is to establish a robust foundation for a European partnership in Cultural Heritage research and innovation (R&I), guided by a holistic framework. It plans to achieve this by creating a coordinated network that brings together scientists, creators, and professionals from Europe and associated countries. Through collaboration, ARCHE aims to facilitate

transnational cooperation and engage all relevant stakeholders and funding mechanisms related to Cultural Heritage R&I policy and action.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

The FSP also coordinates the ARCHE project, which aims to supplement the JPI CH activities with a new tool to rationalise national research policies and include new actors. In this regard, the E-RIHS community is at the frontlines and brings in HS actors such as CNR, CSIC, CYI and ZVKDS.

PRESENT STATUS

Approach

E-RIHS IP and ARCHE share the same overall aim: preparing, creating, and implementing an international initiative for Cultural Heritage research in the ERA frame, respectively, an ERIC and a Partnership. These two initiatives, though of different legal status, duration, and objectives, have common challenges:

- Create an efficient governance structure;
- Define a long-term and sustainable scientific strategy;
- Attract future partners through an ambitious enlargement plan.

These challenges create a common ground for synergies, exchanges, and collaboration.

Areas of collaboration

Examples of areas of collaboration:

- Investigation on EU Cultural Heritage R&I (ARCHE Task 1.4) and on Cultural Heritage programmes in MS/AC (ARCHE Task 1.5);
- Collaboration in fine-tuning E-RIHS IP user strategy;
- Sharing good practices as regards enlargement plans: E-RIHS IP (Tasks 2.2, 4.2 and 6.3) and ARCHE (Task 4.2);
- Alignment of communication actions on subjects of common interest.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Taking into consideration the future RCH Partnership, the collaboration will be fine-tuned. The RCH Partnership fiche indicates that cooperation with RIs such as E-RIHS (as well as with DARIAH, CLARIN and the forthcoming Cultural Heritage Cloud) must be considered. The future ARCHE physical Stakeholders' workshop planned for September 2024 in Florence – joined with E-RIHS IP final event – will tackle this subject more thoroughly and help strengthen E-RIHS and ARCHE respective positions.

E-RIHS WITHIN THE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES ECOSYSTEM

In this section, we describe multilateral cooperation activities with relevant ESFRI projects and landmarks at EU and global level, falling into the Social and Cultural Innovation (CLARIN, DARIAH, OPERAS), Physical Sciences and Engineering (C-ERIC) and Environment (DiSSCo) categories, that aim towards the establishment of common practices and policies and to strengthen E-RIHS excellence and increase the critical mass.

C-ERIC

C-ERIC (Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium) is an ERIC integrating and providing open access to some of the most advanced analytical facilities from 8 countries in Europe in all fields of materials, biomaterials and nanotechnology.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

C-ERIC was already a partner in E-RIHS PP project, with a long-term ongoing collaboration regarding access policy, provision of services and best practices.

PRESENT STATUS

Both C-ERIC and E-RIHS participate in the Italian ERIC Forum of RIs. The Director General of C-ERIC Jana Kolar has participated in several project meetings of E-RIHS IP to build upon the previous successful collaborations. The C-ERIC Deputy Director Ornella di Giacomo is a member of the Research Infrastructure Advisory Board of E-RIHS IP. The Board aims at advising on best practices for managing ERICs, providing feedback on the E-RIHS IP project, recommending strategies for effective implementation and operation of the E-RIHS infrastructure, and suggesting solutions for emerging challenges (see <https://www.e-rihs.eu/ip-advisory-board/>). Furthermore, a dedicated meeting was organized between the teams of E-RIHS and C-ERIC. In its initial stages, this initiative focused on exchanging views for developing a dashboard for access, which included addressing specific technical issues related to digital development of the dashboard itself. The idea behind was to explore the development of a consistent and intuitive user interface, harmonizing the user experience in accessing the facilities of RIs.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Define concrete actions based in previous trajectory of exchanges and prepare action to sign MoU with E-RIHS IP.

CLARIN ERIC

CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure, <https://www.clarin.eu>) is an ERIC supporting the sharing, use and sustainability of digital language resources (data and tools) for research Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

E-RIHS and CLARIN have collaborated and continue to collaborate within the SSHOC cluster (see dedicated session to SSHOC, page 17) for the exchange of best practices, particularly with reference to data in the SSH.

PRESENT STATUS

In addition to SSHOC, E-RIHS collaborates with CLARIN in the framework of ECHOES, the European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science, the European project that aims at setting up the ECCCH, the European Collaborative Cloud on Cultural Heritage (see dedicated session to ECCCH, page 15). Furthermore, at the national level, it is worth mentioning the H2IOSC project, Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it>). Funded by the Next Generation EU's Resilient and Recovery Facility in Italy, the H2IOSC project is spearheaded by the Italian node of E-RIHS.it and collaborates with CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, and OPERAS-IT. These four Italian nodes are dedicated to advancing Humanities research. H2IOSC aims to provide an open, multidisciplinary platform that offers access to sophisticated tools for innovative and

computationally intensive research on complex digital data. By endorsing open science principles, H2IOSC strives to set a national standard for open and interoperable digital research ecosystems to scale it up at the European level.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Moving forward, CLARIN and E-RIHS might explore targeted collaborations that enhance the missions of both infrastructures. Future initiatives will leverage CLARIN's capacity to offer multilingual services, enriching E-RIHS's engagement with diverse national communities. These synergistic efforts will aim to advance a shared vision of promoting open and interoperable digital research ecosystems, benefiting from each infrastructure's unique strengths in supporting comprehensive Cultural Heritage research.

DARIAH ERIC

DARIAH (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities, <https://www.dariah.eu>) develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure in support of ICT-based research practices and sustains researchers operating in humanities in using them to build, analyse and interpret digital resources that connects several hundreds of scholars and dozens of research facilities in more than 20 European countries.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

DARIAH was a partner in E-RIHS PP project (H2020-INFRADEV, GA n. 739503, 2017-2020), with their main involvement regarding to strategies for human resources. E-RIHS and DARIAH have collaborated and continue to collaborate within the SSHOC cluster (see dedicated session to SSHOC, page 17) for the exchange of best practices, particularly with reference to data in the SSH.

PRESENT STATUS

Besides SSHOC, E-RIHS and DARIAH also collaborate on the ECHOES project, which aims to establish the ECCCH, the European Collaborative Cloud on Cultural Heritage (for more details, see the dedicated ECCCH session, page 15). In addition, both organizations participate in the H2IOSC project, the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (for more information, visit <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it>). Additionally, Jennifer Edmond, a former DARIAH Board of Directors member now serves on the Research Infrastructure Advisory Board of E-RIHS IP, offering strategic guidance for E-RIHS's development as an ERIC. More about this advisory role can be found at the webpage, <https://www.e-rihs.eu/ip-advisory-board/>.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Moving forward, the collaboration between E-RIHS and DARIAH is set to intensify, driven by node-level initiatives like Italy's project of H2IOSC, along with new collaborations emerging, for instance, in Poland. The collaboration between E-RIHS and DARIAH is expected to be focused on a more integrated approach to digital data for Cultural Heritage. This direction will likely include interactions with established European initiatives such as EUROPEANA (data space for Cultural Heritage), the ECCCH, along with EOSC, particularly within its emerging thematic nodes. The future perspectives will aim at improving data sharing and interoperability across Europe, supporting a cohesive approach to research in the humanities and Cultural Heritage sectors.

DiSSCo

DiSSCo, the Distributed System of Scientific Collections, is a RI that digitally unifies all European natural science assets, from natural history museums, botanic gardens and university collections, sharing common access, curation, policies and practices across countries while ensuring that all the data complies with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). It is currently on the process of becoming an ERIC.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

A letter of intent for collaboration was signed in 2018 within the framework of E-RIHS PP to start with the definition of synergies and potential areas of collaboration such as sharing knowledge best practices, analytical approaches, digital data management and effective benchmarking.

PRESENT STATUS

Informal discussions with DiSSCo colleagues are underway, and talks at the level of National Nodes are ongoing to enhance collaboration between the two infrastructures, in accordance with the framework outlined in the letter of intent signed in 2018.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Definition of possible collaboration include the use of E-RIHS and DiSSCo access services to enhance research capabilities in fields such as archaeozoology, geoarchaeology, and paleoethnobotany, and in general, in all interdisciplinary fields that integrate the study of cultural and natural heritage, allowing for a more holistic understanding of human history and the environment. Prepare action to sign MoU with E-RIHS IP.

OPERAS

OPERAS, the Open scholarly communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities, is a distributed RI for the coordination and federation of resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH. It is on the path to becoming operational as an ERIC in 2028.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

E-RIHS and OPERAS have collaborated and continue to collaborate within the SSHOC cluster (see dedicated session to SSHOC, page 17) for the exchange of best practices, particularly with reference to data in the SSH.

PRESENT STATUS

Besides SSHOC, E-RIHS and OPERAS also collaborate on the H2IOSC project, the Humanities and Cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (for more information, visit <https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it>). E-RIHS and OPERAS have also collaborated on joint proposals in response to competitive calls aimed at enhancing the utilization of FAIR data and scientific publications within the Heritage Science domain.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Future collaboration between E-RIHS and OPERAS could focus on enhancing open access to scientific papers also in conjunction with the forthcoming E-RIHS DIGILAB, creating added-value for Heritage Science research.

E-RIHS WITHIN THE OPEN CLOUD ECOSYSTEM AND OTHER DIGITAL INITIATIVES

Beyond data FAIRification, the mission of E-RIHS ERIC and neighbouring initiatives is to boost the digital transition of HS and Cultural Heritage domains by creating new opportunities for research, innovation and education across their different systems and platforms within the open cloud ecosystem. In this section we describe the connections of E-RIHS with ECCCH, EOSC, EUROPEANA, OpenAIRE-Nexus, SSHOC, and 4CH.

ECCCH

In June 2022, the European Commission announced its plans to create a future European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH), also known as the Cultural Heritage Cloud. This initiative is designed to connect various Heritage institutions and professionals through a platform that enables a better understanding, documentation, and preservation of Heritage across Europe.

In its largest investment ever made for Cultural Heritage, the Commission allocated a budget of €110M until 2025 through calls for proposals under the Horizon Europe Cluster 2. A first call for proposals was opened in 2023 to finance the creation of the infrastructure itself, a corresponding legal entity with a clear business model and support for integrating the results of the other ECCCH-funded and other relevant data sources, such as E-RIHS.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

Although this high-level initiative is recent, clear links exist between the objectives and vision of the Cloud and those of E-RIHS, and in particular of its DIGILAB. This was facilitated by the publication of an ex-ante expert report on the ECCCH written by experts with good knowledge of DIGILAB and, for one person, a member of the E-RIHS Implementation Phase project.

PRESENT STATUS

Under the leadership of CNRS and with the support of CNR and FSP, the European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science (ECHOES) project was developed and has been awarded €25M to implement its vision based on the co-creation of Heritage Digital Twins within Digital Commons in an open, integrative digital ecosystem. This project started on June 2024, and is set to last 5 years.

Beyond the three leading institutions that have leading roles in their respective E-RIHS National Nodes, ECHOES involves key DIGILAB actors: KIK-IRPA (Belgium), CYI, Cergy Paris Université (France), FORTH (Greece), the National Gallery (UK). It also involves several other research infrastructures, IGO or networks active in the field of Cultural Heritage, such as DARIAH, CLARIN, ARIADNE RI, ICOM, ICOMS, E.C.C.O, APEF, etc.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

This focus on research infrastructures and networks and, more generally, on building upon existing initiatives and services should prove beneficial to DIGILAB's development and valorisation. The opening in June 2024 of the new ECCCH Horizon Europe calls for proposals provides a new opportunity for coordinated proposals from the E-RIHS community, together with the soon-to-be-established E-RIHS ERIC.

EOSC

EOSC, the European Open Science Cloud (<https://eosc.eu>), is a pan-European virtual environment for sharing and accessing research data across borders and scientific disciplines.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

Commitment of E-RIHS to promote open access and FAIR principles in the Heritage Science.

PRESENT STATUS

E-RIHS participates in the SSHOC Cluster, one of the five science clusters in the context of EOSC (see the chapter dedicated to SSHOC, page 17).

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Cooperating on future initiatives in the domain for the benefit of the current development of E-RIHS DIGILAB, and also to make Heritage Science data more FAIR—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Through open access, this collaboration aims to create new knowledge and broaden the impact of Heritage Science.

EUROPEANA

Europeana is Europe's digital platform, which was launched by the European Commission in 2008 to support the Cultural Heritage sector in its digital transformation. It develops skills, tools and strategies to embrace digital change and offers free access to digitised contributions from recognised cultural institutions of the Member States for education, research, creation and recreation. Europeana is the coordinator of the Data Space for Cultural Heritage, an initiative funded by the Digital Europe Programme focused on accelerating the digital transition of Europe's cultural and creative industries.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

Although Europeana and E-RIHS share common interests in documenting, understanding, and valorising Cultural Heritage through digital means, no joint activities have been carried out to this date. At the moment, E-RIHS is not involved in deploying the Data Space on Cultural Heritage.

PRESENT STATUS

High-level dialogue between the Europeana Foundation and the lead E-RIHS DIGILAB partners was started during the preparation of the ECHOES project (see the ECCCH section, page 15), of which Europeana is a member. This dialogue covered data interoperability, community engagement, and joint training opportunities.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The creation of the ECCCH will provide a meeting place for E-RIHS and Europeana to collaborate. In particular, joint community engagement and training resources could be developed on digital Cultural Heritage.

OPENAIRE-NEXUS

The Heritage Science Gateway developed with OpenAIRE CONNECT provides open access to relevant research outcomes in this field (scientific publications, datasets, software, etc.).

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

During the IPERION HS project, CNR-INO signed a MoU with OpenAIRE in the framework of the OpenAIRE-Nexus project. The collaboration aimed to facilitate the discovery of research products in the domain of Heritage Science and track the research outputs of the community. As a result, the outcomes were the creation of two gateways with related Monitor dashboards:

IPERION HS Connect gateway

- <https://iperionhs.openaire.eu/>
- <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/iperionhs>

Heritage Science Connect gateway

- <https://heritage-science.openaire.eu/>
- <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/heritage-science>

PRESENT STATUS

In line with the E-RIHS community objective to become a global research infrastructure, CNR asked OpenAIRE to continue the collaboration by transferring the “Heritage Science” Connect gateway to E-RIHS ERIC as a legacy. The gateway represents a single-entry point to discover research outputs in the field of Heritage Science, while the Monitor dashboard allows for monitoring the performance of the field and the fairness of the community.

OpenAIRE and E-RIHS will work together to ease the discovery of research products in the domain of Heritage Science and track the research outputs of the HS community. The collaboration will provide valuable statistics and indicators useful for reporting, enabling the monitoring of the impact of the community in the research landscape and its contribution to Open Science. OpenAIRE will also help the HS community to increase the visibility of the HS research outputs at global level in communities working in different fields and fostering open science practices.

The OpenAIRE-Nexus initiative concluded at the end of 2023. OpenAIRE is currently working on formalizing the Connect and Monitor services, including financial implications. Now, E-RIHS is awaiting additional details regarding the terms and conditions of the services, as well as the signing of a new MoU.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Looking ahead, the OpenAIRE Connect and Monitor services play a crucial role in providing a comprehensive understanding of the complex, multidisciplinary community of Heritage Science. These services also enable the monitoring of its progress, allowing for the evaluation of scientific strategies and fostering innovation within the community.

SSHOC

SSHOC, Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (see <https://sshopencloud.eu>), is a network of interconnected data infrastructures participated by ESFRI landmarks and projects operating in the Social Sciences and Humanities domain, including E-RIHS.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

SSHOC was established to preserve, sustain, and exploit the outputs of the SSHOC project over the long term. Participants in this project included E-RIHS partner organizations, notably CNR (Italy), FORTH (Greece) and the National Gallery (UK). These organizations collaborated within the broader

framework of SSHOC to create a robust European open cloud ecosystem for the social sciences and humanities. This ecosystem integrates technical and social components to maximize the re-use of SSH data, adhering to Open Science and FAIR principles.

PRESENT STATUS

E-RIHS signed the MoU for participating in SSHOC together with ESFRI landmarks and projects operating in the Social Sciences and Humanities domain. The MoU aims to establish the SSH Open Cluster, enhancing cooperation among stakeholders in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) within the European Research Area and globally. This initiative seeks to boost the impact and visibility of SSH research by fostering interactions, sharing expertise, and exploring synergies. Key goals include optimizing resource use across SSH communities, addressing shared challenges, and simplifying interactions with European Commission and other EU bodies. The MoU also focuses on improving joint visibility, advocating for SSH interests through entities like the EOSC, and acting as a central contact point for collaborations with global scientific organizations. Overall, this effort will strengthen the SSH domain's sustainability, impact, and unified representation to a broad audience, including national governments and international stakeholders.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

SSHOC is one of the five scientific clusters of European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). E-RIHS's participation in SSHOC is strategically aimed at contributing to the SSHOC marketplace services (<https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace>) and ensuring that developments within the E-RIHS DIGILAB are aligned and interoperable with the broader European ecosystem. This collaboration will not only contribute to SSHOC's thematic services within EOSC but also facilitate the exchange of best practices for advancements in E-RIHS DIGILAB.

4CH

4CH, the Competence Centre for the Conservation of Cultural Heritage, will launch a central hub for the provision of services, tools and methods for the conservation, preservation and valorisation of historical monuments and sites, which, in turn, will activate, upon needs and competences, regional representatives, primarily consortium members which participated in the EU-funded project 4CH, (under Grant Agreement n.101004468 – 4CH, which include institutions from the academia, industry, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and research centres) with complementary expertise and a wide geographic coverage of Europe. The Consortium is open to cooperation with heritage agencies and ministries, research centres and SMEs willing to pursue Cultural Heritage conservation, preservation and valorisation through digital, primarily 3D technologies.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

The possible structure and the operational framework of 4CH was first introduced by its coordinator to all IPERION HS partners at the 1st annual meeting (April 2021). (<https://zenodo.org/records/6539083>).

PRESENT STATUS

Cooperation agreement in the form of a MoU is currently being explored.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Cooperation on sharing knowledge and expertise on tools, methods, protocols and workflows related to the use of digital technologies in conservation of built heritage and developing new ones.

Request of services from E-RIHS' platform (e.g. portable instrumentation from MOLAB to conduct in-situ investigations primarily in projects on conservation / preservation of built heritage, sites and monuments, sample analysis at FIXLAB platform laboratories or consultation of material in ARCHLAB.

Advancement on training and upskilling programs, and/or sharing best practices and guidelines could be among the future initiatives to further build upon.

E-RIHS AND OTHER EUROPEAN ORGANIZATIONS

The Cooperation Strategy of E-RIHS also envisages a framework for the development of collaborations with pan-European alliances, such as EASSH as detailed below.

EASSH

EASSH, the European Alliance for Social Sciences and Humanities (<https://eassh.eu>), is the largest advocacy and science policy organisation for the social sciences and humanities in Europe. The alliance has 70 member organizations, including a wide range of disciplinary areas, stakeholders and universities from across Europe – and encompassing over 100,000 researchers.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

EASSH has established longstanding partnerships with Research Infrastructures operating within the realms of social sciences and humanities. CLARIN, DARIAH, and ESS actively engage as members of EASSH, with the aim of fostering discourse and advocating for research within the social sciences and humanities.

PRESENT STATUS

EASSH has been actively engaged as a key participant in the stakeholder involvement initiative launched by ESFRI. This collaboration is part of a strategic effort to compile the comprehensive Landscape Analysis 2024. As leading advocates for SSH in Europe, EASSH provides E-RIHS with a vital platform for addressing Heritage Science issues and expanding its user base.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

By becoming a member of EASSH, E-RIHS will be able to contribute Heritage Science perspectives to SSH advocacy efforts across Europe and broaden its impact. This membership will provide a forum for engaging with potential and diverse users of E-RIHS, and for identifying emerging needs from humanities scholars who are part of EASSH.

E-RIHS AND INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIONS

To enable the development of the future “Global E-RIHS”, the reinforcement of existing international connections established in the last 20 years and the expansion of international partnerships are key. Cooperation actions aimed at continuously building the global dimension of HS and strengthening and structuring this research area focus on organisations, projects and infrastructures in America, North Africa, China and the Middle East. E-RIHS ERIC will fully exploit

these synergies and will foster new partnerships. Here we describe these connections and the status of cooperation with E-RIHS.

CHINA

Communication and association between the E-RIHS partners and China refers to a number of common actions and initiatives that carefully and systematically cultivate common understanding and collaborative research actions towards the study and protection of Heritage assets. These refer to the contribution of E-RIHS partners to the dialogues initiated by the Chinese government through Taihe civilizations Fora, the development of joint laboratory alliances, and the signature of framework agreements.

TCF, Taihe Civilizations Forum

Taihe symbolizes the ancient wisdom of life which guides people to rediscover the true meaning of their world. The purpose of Taihe is to obtain continuous wisdom and momentum through the creation of common values (<http://www.titcf.org/about/>).

The Taihe Civilizations Forum (TCF) has been initiated in 2017 to engage global leaders of all fields in supporting "the harmonious development of common values and the advancement of human civilization". The TCF focuses on global and regional challenges, explores root causes, identifies and promotes possible solutions, as well as facilitates communication and impacts creation across borders.

Taihe Civilizations Forum 2023

From July to October 2023, TCF held a series of sub-sessions in various Chinese cities with thematic around topics of cultural exchanges and mutual appreciation of civilizations under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), multilateral cooperation in energy, challenges and opportunities in the evolution of the international landscape and order, vocational education development strategy, talent integration between Hong Kong and the Greater Bay Area, and digital China construction. Esteemed experts and scholars from both China and around the world were invited to share and engage in intellectual discourse.

Within this scheme the sixth "Taihe Forum" around the theme "International Exchange, Cooperation and Sharing in Cultural Heritage Protection" was organized by the Palace Museum in cooperation with the Forbidden City Cultural Heritage Conservation Foundation and the Forbidden City Society of China, on 15 to 18 October 2023 in Beijing. The Forum aimed at bringing together heads of institutions or scholars from China, France, Greece, Italy, Japan, Portugal, the United States, Uzbekistan and other countries, as well as experts from relevant international organizations, to discuss their experience in international cooperation projects, academic exchanges, talent development, and institution building in recent years. Among its aims was also to enhance the understanding of the current landscape and trends in Cultural Heritage protection and promote the comparative study of concepts, standards, technologies and methods, thus contributing to international cooperation, exchange and sharing. Within the 6th FORUM the following Sessions were arranged:

Session I: Conservation of Cultural Heritage-International Interaction

Sessions II-IV: Conservation of Cultural Heritage and International Cooperation (Parts 1, 2 & 3)

Session V: Conservation of Cultural Heritage and International Sharing

E-RIHS consortium was represented in this forum by:

- Prof. Spiros Anastasiadis, Department of Chemistry, University of Crete and IESL-FORTH, GREECE, “The Greek experience of international cooperation for the protection of Cultural Heritage”,
- Prof. António Candeias, Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry of the School of Sciences and Technology, University of Évora, PORTUGAL, “International cooperation and transnational networks and sharing of human and analytical resources - the experience of Hercules Laboratory”,
- Prof. Vincent Detalle, Cergy Paris Université, former Senior Conservation Scientist the Ministry of Culture, France, “The ESPADON Project: A New Dynamics and Paradigm Shift for Heritage Science?”.

Joint Research Laboratories with Chinese Institutions

The Belt and Road Initiative (also known as the One Belt One Road or the New Silk Road), is a global infrastructure development strategy adopted by the Chinese government in 2013 to invest in more than 150 countries and international organizations. The Belt and Road Initiative forms a central component of the Chinese leader Xi Jinping's "Major Country Diplomacy" strategy, which calls for China to assume a greater leadership role for global affairs in accordance with its rising power and status.

In 2020, The Chinese government launched a call for their creation of Joint Laboratories between Chinese institutions and international leading institutions in all fields of knowledge aiming to exchange and cooperate in science and technology for shared benefit. Among the 40 Joint Laboratories created, only 2 were created in the field of Cultural Heritage conservation, and both with members of E-RIHS and here briefly presented hereafter:

- The **China-Greece Joint Laboratory on Cultural Heritage Conservation Technology Construction**, a consortium between the Palace Museum (in Beijing) and FORTH.
- The **China-Portugal Joint Laboratory on Cultural Heritage Conservation Science**, a consortium between the Soochow University, the City University of Macau and HERCULES Laboratory from Evora University.

China-Greece Joint Laboratory on Cultural Heritage Conservation Technology Construction

China-Greece joint laboratory on Cultural Heritage Conservation Technology refers to the collaboration of IESL/FORTH and the Palace Museum for the Construction and development of a laboratory on laser analysis and conservation at the premises of the Palace Museum (PM), Forbidden City, Beijing, China.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

Discussions on the potential collaboration between Greece and China were initiated back in 2015. On July 2016 the then Greek Prime Minister, Alexis Tsipras, and the minister of Research, C. Fotakis, visited to China for the inauguration of the common laboratory “Niki: China – Greece Laser Technology joint laboratory on Cultural Heritage” at PM. On November 2019 the Chinese President visited the Acropolis Museum in Athens and got impressed by the demo of the laser cleaning intervention (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kRJ28Nq0OZA>). On 2020 the project on the joint laboratory development was initiated and through this initiative a number of visits were realized to date. Highlights in this collaboration are the workshop “Laser Technology for Analysis and Conservation of Heritage Objects” organized at the PM, Beijing on 25-27/09/2023 in which keynote speakers were P. Pouli and D. Anglos from IESL-FORTH and C. Vasiliadis from the Acropolis Museum.

Within this course prof. D. Anglos discussed on “Heritage Science in Greece and Europe; the role of the ecosystem of FORTH and the University of Crete” in a public event titled “Heritage Science: A global driver for sustainability” which was livestreamed and had well over 2000 attendees (100 in the lecture hall and the rest online).

PRESENT STATUS

The collaboration approach is based on joint research, common educational activities and staff exchanges within the area of laser cleaning and laser analysis. The first MoU was signed on February 2017 and a recent one was signed on 7th of November 2023, on the occasion of the visit of the director of PM, Mr. Wang Xudong, in the premises of FORTH, in Heraklion, Crete, Greece.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

A joint proposal entitled “Applied research and innovative methodologies on laser cleaning technology for stone heritage between China and Greece”, aiming at the continuation of PM-FORTH collaboration, was submitted on 20/12/2023, in the framework of the call “INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY INNOVATION BETWEEN GOVERNMENTS -NATIONAL KEY RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT PLAN’. FORTH will submit also a proposal in the Greek-Chinese bilateral call, which is expected to be released in spring 2024.

China-Portugal Joint Laboratory on Cultural Heritage Conservation Science

China-Portugal Joint Laboratory on Cultural Heritage Conservation Science (CP-LCHCS) refers to the collaboration between the Soochow University, the City University of Macau and HERCULES Laboratory from Evora University to develop key methodologies to address significant research questions and scientific challenges in Cultural Heritage conservation and sustainable development.

PRESENT STATUS

Joint research activities CP-LCHS aim at advancing the knowledge and capacities of CP-LCHCS beyond the state-of-the-art, ensuring long-lasting competitiveness of the research infrastructure developed within the laboratory. Particularly the laboratory is focused on cooperatively carrying out research activities in the following three areas of Cultural Heritage Conservation Science: Cultural Heritage material analysis and new technologies research, research on urban and architectural heritage and sustainable development, traditional craft and industrial innovation research. This has been achieved through specific research projects, internships and staff mobility (2 researchers from the Joint Lab have made 1 year mobility at HERCULES Lab, 4 members of HERCULES Lab have been for 2 weeks in China), training programs (HERCULES Lab staff has organized 4 hands-on workshops on non-invasive analysis in 4 Universities in China: Soochow University, Fujian University of Technology, Taiyuan University of Technology and City University of Macau), organization and participation in joint conferences (3) and co-supervision of post-graduate students (2 Erasmus Mundus Master students).

Due to the historical Portuguese influence, Macau has been a special link connecting China and Portugal and therefore special efforts have been made regarding research on shared heritage and the creation of a research analytical infrastructure at City University of Macau with consultancy from HERCULES members. In fact, a specific project has been presented to Macau Science Foundation that allowed the setup of a lab equipped with some portable (EDXRF, X-ray radiography, FTIR) and microanalysis (OM, SEM-EDS).

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The Joint Lab is operating normally, and it is expected that some members of HERCULES Lab will become Visiting Professors at Soochow University and City University of Macau during the present year thus ensuring a close cooperation and the development of joint activities.

Chinese-French Collaboration on Heritage Science

Since 2016, the FSP has signed multiple cooperation agreements with Chinese cultural institutions involving E-RIHS France partners (C2RMF, LRMH, Cergy Paris Université, CNRS, and INP) together with other French cultural institutions. These agreements have created working relationships between several French and Chinese teams of Heritage Scientists, curators, and conservators-restorers leading to joint training activities and events and the publication of an official French Chinese glossary on Cultural Heritage

PRESENT STATUS

The latest instalments of this collaboration undertaken by FSP on behalf of several E-RIHS France members focus on the Shaanxi province, especially the study and preservation of the terracotta army in Xi'an, the conservation of granite sculptures in both countries and joint training workshops for conservators-restorers. Another ongoing project addresses common challenges in mural painting conservation, focusing on the Mogao Caves in Dunhuang, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, with the active participation of the French MOLAB and several study visits are planned in both countries.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The aforementioned Greek, Portuguese and French collaborations with China will eventually enable E-RIHS to develop its own activities (e.g. networking, joint events, etc.).

Confucius-Aristotle Symposium on Ancient Wisdom for Modern Challenges

The Confucius-Aristotle Symposium on Ancient Wisdom for Modern Challenges will take place during July 8-12, 2024, in Qufu and Beijing, China. Qufu is the birthplace of Confucius and a unique venue for world-leading thinkers to draw the connections of our ancient wisdom traditions with our pressing 21st-century challenges.

The Symposium will take place in advance of the World Congress of Philosophy in Rome (August 1-8, 2024) and the UN Summit of the Future in NYC (September 22-23, 2024) and will aim to contribute insights to those two important forthcoming events.

This is the third in the series of global meetings bringing together philosophers, policy experts, and leaders in the new digital technologies, to consider the meeting points and divergences of the ancient wisdom traditions, and to consider how we can draw on this vast bounty of knowledge to help us confront challenges such as the environmental crises, challenges of war and peace, and governance over the new cutting-edge technologies. Most importantly, the Symposium seeks to identify common heritage and shared values, aiming to promote peace and cooperation in the 21st century. The interim Director General of E-RIHS is among the speakers of the Symposium.

EGYPT

Egypt boasts a rich heritage that holds universal interest due to its profound impact on human civilization throughout history. Egypt is renowned for its ancient civilization, which flourished over 5,000 years ago. This civilization left behind iconic monuments and developed one of the earliest

forms of writing as well as cultural legacy extends beyond antiquity and encompasses contributions to fields such as mathematics, medicine, astronomy, and literature. Egypt remains a treasure trove for archaeologists and heritage scientists, with ongoing excavations and Heritage Science research uncovering new insights into its ancient past with contributions by many national and international expeditions from France, UK, Italy, Spain, Germany, etc. Egypt has developed capacity of HS through new institutions, academic programmes, research infrastructure, publications, and trainings, as well as regional cooperation at the Arab and African scales. Ain Shams University in Egypt is one of the leading institutions in the field of Heritage Science where its experts lead the approach to E-RIHS.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

E-RIHS has established contacts in Egypt since 2019. In 2019, E-RIHS was promoted in Egypt through a visit by Matija Strlic (Director of Operations of E-RIHS PP) to the Egypt-Japan University of Science and Technology (E-JUST), where a Master's degree programme and a centre of excellence of HS were established and coordinated by Abdelrazek Elnaggar. Following the visit, Abdelrazek Elnaggar presented the landscape of Heritage Science in Egypt at the E-RIHS meeting in Evora, Portugal in 2019. After the meeting, Egypt received a welcome package from E-RIHS. Egypt was invited to the E-RIHS Interim Committee of National Nodes (iCNN) and Enlargement Board (EB) meetings and was introduced by Mamdouh Eldamaty (Professor of Archaeological Sciences at Ain Shams University (ASU) and former Egyptian Minister of Antiquities). In December 2023, Egyptian heritage institutions met with members of the E-RIHS Slovenian Board and Polona Ropret, the Chair of the E-RIHS iCNN and the EB for a conference at the Egyptian Academy of Scientific Research and Technology (ASRT) to discuss Egypt's expectations and offers to E-RIHS and to learn from the experiences of the Slovenian node. A memorandum of understanding between ASU and the Slovenian Node of E-RIHS is in preparation in order to enhance further cooperation. Egypt's expectations and offers were presented to the iCNN and the EB at the E-RIHS meeting in Madrid in March 2024. Egypt has also received access projects via IPERION HS Transnational Access program.

PRESENT STATUS

Actions to be determined soon through the communications between E-RIHS iCNN/EB and Egypt representatives.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The prospects for collaboration across different areas can be summarized as follows:

- Exchange of students, researchers and professionals via bilateral or multilateral agreements;
- Exchange of experiences and expertise in tackling Cultural Heritage issues in diverse levels;
- Conception and promotion of joint research projects;
- Organisation and promotion of dissemination and networking events, workshops, and trainings. Egypt can act as a gateway to broader Arab region and Africa.

LATIN AMERICAN AND CARIBBEAN COUNTRIES

Brazil: ANTECIPA

ANTECIPA (Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio/Brazilian National Association for Research in Technology and Heritage Science) was founded in December 2015 with the main objective of promoting the preservation of Cultural Heritage through

interdisciplinary collaboration between individuals and institutions from several areas working in Cultural Heritage.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

Integration with the European projects was effective since the EU-ARTECH project, back in the years 2000, when LACICOR at the Federal University of Minas Gerais was invited to join.

PRESENT STATUS

Within the framework of IPERION HS, ANTECIPA has participated and collaborated with the meetings and discussions of the DIGILAB working group. ANTECIPA has also organized, in Brazil, a workshop and pilot activity dealing with data interoperability, with focus on Scanning Electron Microscope – Energy Dispersive Spectrometer (SEM-EDS), to understand and map the processes and problems of sharing scientific analytical data and propose possible solutions to share data correctly and comply with FAIR principles.

In December 2023 the Brazilian IN2PAST.BR was created. The recently approved IN2PAST.BR (National Institute for Research in Natural History, Cultural Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory) is the very first Brazilian institute focused on multidisciplinary historical research and the protection of heritage. The institute IN@PAST BR is part of a Brazilian network of excellence research centers and is associated with Portuguese Lab IN2PAST (Associated Lab for Research and Innovation in Heritage, Arts, Sustainability and Territory) coordinated by HERCULES Lab, participating in IPERION HS. This institute is based on HS as an expanded, transdisciplinary and strategic field of knowledge, capable of conducting scientific research that enables the sustainable management of cultural and natural assets in the Brazilian context, by an academic network associated with public bodies such as the Federal Police and the Federal Public Prosecutor's Office. To this end, the project is based on the creation of a shared scientific infrastructure and the generation of a scientific database on heritage assets, with a view to identifying and/or recovering stolen, trafficked or damaged materials and pieces, as well as to help the decision processes in terms of conservation management. The main thematic lines are: 1. anthropological/archaeological heritage, in the field of Physical Anthropology and Archaeometry; 2. natural heritage, with studies of paleontological and biological objects (biodiversity); 3. analytical and informational technologies applied to museum objects and other collections, including issues of the Technical Art History, Genetic Heritage and Conservation Science; 4. Information Management, considering the interoperability of scientific data. The project coordination is based at the Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG) and includes collaboration with the National Criminalistics Institute of the Federal Police, the Forensic Science Centre of the Federal University of Paraná, the Stable Isotopes Centre of the State University of São Paulo, between other universities and research centers around the country.

A letter of collaboration to become a strategic partner of E-RIHS was issued by ANTECIPA in December 2023.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

The prospects for collaboration across different areas can be summarized as follows:

- Access via bilateral or multilateral agreements to respective infra-structure platforms;
- Conception and promotion of joint research projects, events, workshops;
- Development of shared databases and access and sharing of heritage sample collections;
- Exchange of students, researchers and professionals via bilateral or multilateral agreements;
- Exchange of experiences and expertise in tackling Cultural Heritage issues in diverse levels.

EU-LAC ResInfra Plus

EU-LAC ResInfra Plus is a Horizon Europe funded project. The former H2020 EU-LAC ResInfra (Dec 2019 – Feb 2023) project served to boost the bi-regional collaboration on research infrastructures (RIs) between European Union (EU) and Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) countries. To this aim a variety of different activities were developed that have proven the importance of RIs as a key pillar in boosting the R&D activities between regions and the need to maintain a sustainable collaboration at governmental level. Despite the success of the results of EU-LAC ResInfra project, as there is still work to do in order to have a solid and sustainable framework of cooperation to enhance the bi-regional collaboration on research infrastructures, the EC decided to fund the project EU-LAC ResInfra Plus (2024 – 2025). EU-LAC ResInfra Plus project aims at boosting the efforts and synergies created during these previous years, adding also new areas in Latin America by including the corresponding agency in Cuba (CITMA), Peru (CONCYTEC) and Argentina (MINCYT). The proposed EU LAC ResInfra Plus project will support the new EU CELAC Strategic Roadmap.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

The former EU-LAC ResInfra project developed four pilots in the four areas selected as priorities areas for the bi-regional collaboration between EU and LAC. The areas were: health (structural biology), TIC (High performance computing), Biodiversity and ecosystems and Cultural Heritage.

The Cultural Heritage pilot, previously mentioned within the framework of IPERION HS (see the ANTECIPA section, page 24), lays the foundations for the construction of a common digital research environment based on the availability of FAIR data on the specific case of spectral data obtained by scanning electron microscopy (SEM-EDS).

PRESENT STATUS

EU-LAC ResInfra Plus will not implement pilots as in the former project, but it is foreseen the organization of several workshops and seminars focused in different areas crucial for the collaboration between the two regions in which E-RIHS could participate.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Collaboration would be in the following areas, among others:

- Promotion of joint research projects, events, workshops;
- Participation in workshops and seminars;
- Collaboration in the surveys launched by EU-LAC ResInfra Plus project;
- To promote/to boost the bi-regional collaboration in the area of Cultural Heritage.

INSTITUTIONS IN THE USA

International contacts of the E-RIHS partnership with USA institutions have been nurtured during IPERION HS and its predecessor projects. Exchanges and dialogue with important USA museums, including The Getty Conservation Institute, The Smithsonian Institution-Museum Conservation Institute, The Metropolitan Museum of New York and The Art Institute of Chicago, have taken place in view of strengthening their interest of participation in a future “Global E-RIHS”. However, during the timespan of the IPERION HS project, all international activities were severely diminished due to the pandemic emergency. Deliverable D.8.4 “Final Report on International Activities” of IPERION HS [12] describes the plan to organize a “Pan-American Workshop on Heritage Science” at the Getty Conservation Institute in Los Angeles in spring 2021, involving all the major Heritage Science hubs in the two American continents. The organization of this in-presence event proved unfeasible during

the first two years of the project (2020 and 2021) and attempts to hold it in 2022 as a hybrid event to be hosted jointly by partners National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) and UFMG were unsuccessful due to the resurgence of the COVID pandemic.

ERIHS ERIC will capitalize on these precedents to reinitiate and build up a relevant portfolio of cooperation activities with actors in this geographical area.

E-RIHS AND INTERGOVERNAMENTAL ORGANIZATIONS

ICCROM

ICCROM, the International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property, is an intergovernmental organization working in service to its member states to promote the conservation of all forms of Cultural Heritage in every region of the world with a broad range of initiatives in training, information, research, cooperation and advocacy.

COLLABORATION BACKGROUND

In 2018, a MoU was signed between E-RIHS and ICCROM, with the latter supporting the development of Heritage Science as a participating member of IPERION HS. Furthermore, ICCROM has contributed to the establishment of E-RIHS as an ERIC by participating in the interim General Assembly of E-RIHS.

PRESENT STATUS

ICCROM currently participates in the E-RIHS IP project by upgrading the user strategy, the catalogue of services, and by participating in outreach activities, among many other tasks. ICCROM has expressed interest in becoming a permanent observer of E-RIHS ERIC once the ERIC is established.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

ICCROM will support E-RIHS ERIC as a permanent observer. There are ongoing discussions on the possibility of ICCROM being a provider of services for E-RIHS (through sample collections).

A LOOK INTO THE FUTURE OF COOPERATION FOR E-RIHS ERIC

In this document, we have reported on the various exchanging activities that have been initiated and strengthened by the E-RIHS IP consortium involving networks and initiatives of various kinds and geographical influence, operating in the physical and natural sciences and in the SSH domains, and which are relevant in the broad area of Heritage Science. These activities are significantly contributing to the HS domain, and will do so in the future, by strengthening the E-RIHS international cooperation, by cultivating synergies and by amalgamating the HS community around E-RIHS. The E-RIHS Cooperation Strategy that was described, in terms of objectives and methodology, in the previous E-RIHS IP deliverable D6.3 “Report on Cooperation Activities: Approach and Advancement” will be the guide to design the future of international cooperation for E-RIHS ERIC.

To develop an effective Cooperation Strategy, E-RIHS ERIC will have to implement meaningful and feasible tools for assessing and evaluating its global leadership in the broad multidisciplinary field

of HS and for ensuring that the RI is capable of addressing HS challenges with a global dimension. In that respect, several recommendations could be made:

1. HS is a highly dynamic domain where new projects and RIs constantly emerge. Therefore, E-RIHS ERIC will have to implement instruments (i.e., a Cooperation Radar) to periodically review and update the landscape of relevant actors that should be engaged with E-RIHS in cooperative actions.
2. E-RIHS ERIC will have to include provisions for international organizations to become participants and for non-EU partners to become observers in the framework of a smart growth strategy that will define the common practices and policies. E-RIHS will integrate new facilities of recognized excellence in HS (based on quality evaluation) and in base at their capacity to offer in-kind access. Their participation in the future E-RIHS ERIC will be formalized through letters of interest or other types of agreements for the role of observer according to guidelines settled in the E-RIHS IP, Task 4.2 E-RIHS Enlargement Strategy [13].
3. E-RIHS ERIC has to define key performance indicators (KPIs) in the particular area of global cooperation [14]. Among them, the number of agreements signed with external actors at European and global level (MoUs, letters of Intent or other types of agreements), number of joint training actions for users and access providers, other networking activities, etc.
4. In the rich and complex global HS ecosystem, it is important to single out the relevance of defining a strategy to align and create synergies with the JPI CH and the forthcoming Alliance for Research on Cultural Heritage in Europe (ARCHE). Coherence between European and national levels in R&I priorities and objectives involves recognising and leveraging the value of diversity among member states and associated countries (MS/AC). JPI CH is a key part of the common vision that the EU and MS/AC share in the research domain of Cultural Heritage and therefore it is then very essential that E-RIHS exploits the full potential of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda of JPI CH and ARCHE. In this respect, the E-RIHS community is actively contributing to the discussions shaping the upcoming European Resilient Cultural Heritage (RCH) partnership, which is currently being prepared at ARCHE. This contribution is made possible through the engagement of various E-RIHS partner organizations in the ARCHE project. Looking ahead, the use of E-RIHS facilities should be facilitated within the framework of research projects funded by RCH, aiming to utilize the state-of-the-art facilities provided by E-RIHS to enhance Heritage Science research.

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